

SDN-Enabled CV-QKD and Classical Channels Coexistence: Key Insights for Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing [Invited]

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Abstract: In this paper, we explored various physical-layer parameters affecting the coexistence of continuous-variable quantum key distribution (CV-QKD) and classical channels (CCs) within a dense wavelength division multiplexing (DWDM) in the C-band. These parameters include *number of transmitted quantum symbols, power levels of CCs, quantum channel (QC) allocation within the C-band, power distribution among CCs, channel spacing between CCs and QC, and CCs power ranges suitable for both CCs and QC*. These insights provide valuable guidance for *software-defined networking (SDN) control system* to manage CV-QKD and CC coexistence effectively. We observed that for short distances and lower key rates, the number of quantum symbols exchanged does not need to reach the asymptotic convergence limit. However, achieving the asymptotic regime on a 10-km link requires transmitting approximately 1×10^{13} quantum symbols. CC power significantly impacts CV-QKD performance. For example, in a DWDM setup with 37 dummy CCs on a 100 GHz grid, CV-QKD can support up to 11 dBm total launch power over 10-km link when the QC is positioned at 193.2 THz and a 200 GHz channel spacing between QC and CCs is maintained. Strategic placement of the QC within the C-band also enhances performance. Placing the QC at higher frequency channels relative to CCs improves both the secret key fraction and the maximum supported power of CCs. For instance, placing the QC at 195.9 THz provides better performance than positioning it at 193.2 THz or 192.2 THz. However, when the QC is placed at 192.2 THz, the maximum supported CC power reduces to 9.8 dBm. Additionally, the relationship between power distribution and power concentration is complex and requires careful consideration. It depends on the number of active CCs, the power of CCs, and their spectral placement relative to the QC. We also analyzed the case of 8×200 G modulated CCs and found out that placing them 100 GHz from the QC introduces nonlinear noise but still allows a positive secret key fraction. Increasing the spacing to 200 GHz further improves CV-QKD performance. Joint performance analysis revealed that, at a 100 GHz spacing and 30 dB optical signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) for CCs, a launch power range of -16.96 to 9.03 dBm supports both error-free CC recovery and positive key rate generation over a 10-km link. This comprehensive analysis highlights the interplay between CV-QKD and CCs, offering practical strategies for optimizing their coexistence in DWDM systems through an *SDN control system*.

Index Terms— Continuous variable quantum key distribution (CV-QKD), coexistence, software defined networking (SDN)

I. INTRODUCTION

Secure communication is essential to meet the requirements of future networks specially in quantum era [1][2]. Quantum key distribution (QKD) stands out as a significant practical application of quantum communication [3] that offers a way to generate cryptographic keys rooted on quantum mechanics and thus provides security against future quantum computers [4]. Most fiber-based QKD experiments rely on dedicated dark fibers, as the noise of the classical channels (CCs) can degrade the performance of the QKD signal. However, in today's telecom landscape, it can be costly and extremely challenging especially in the access segment for network operators to use fiber optic cable exclusively for quantum communication [5]. Therefore, most fiber infrastructure is shared by multiple services to maximize efficiency and reduce costs, and QKD must ideally work in conjunction with CCs, such as wavelength-division multiplexing (WDM) fiber links. WDM combines multiple optical signals on a single fiber by using different wavelengths of light to transmit each signal simultaneously [6].

Continuous-variable QKD (CV-QKD) [7] is a promising approach in the field of quantum cryptography. Unlike discrete-

variable QKD, which relies on the use of single photons [8], CV-QKD employs continuous variables such as the quadratures of the electromagnetic field. Due to its high efficiency in the C-band [9] and the use of coherent detection technology [10], widely adopted in optical communication, CV-QKD fits well with modern-day optical networks. CV-QKD has some challenges which are thoroughly covered theoretically in literature. As the transmission rate increases, CV-QKD moves from a single-mode to a continuous-mode regime, requiring digital signal processing (DSP) techniques to recover quadrature information. This shift introduces security challenges, particularly in the presence of multi-point DSP processing, which necessitates a theoretical framework to ensure security and has been covered in [11]. Furthermore, the impact of receiver bandwidth constraints on CV-QKD systems must be considered, as an insufficient bandwidth can lead to inaccurate estimation of transmission loss and excess noise, affecting key rate performance [12].

Previous studies have also investigated the experimental coexistence of CV-QKD in fixed networks with a spacing of 100 GHz following the international telecommunication union (ITU). In [13], for example, the coexistence of CV-QKD with

7×12.5 Gbit/s on-off keying was demonstrated. The research in [14] investigated CV-QKD together with 4×100 Gb/s and 16×10 Gb/s classical telecom signals. Other studies, such as [15], demonstrated CV-QKD with 89 CCs spaced 1 nm apart in the C-band over a 7-core fiber. However, these studies analyzed the impact of classical signals on CV-QKD, often neglecting critical aspects of having efficient joint quantum-classical coexistence. In particular, issues such as error-free recovery—measured in terms of bit error rate (BER)—in CCs and the power thresholds required for error-free transmission over different distances, have not been thoroughly addressed [16][17]. To optimize coexistence scenarios, it is essential to perform a comprehensive analysis that considers both classical and CV-QKD signals and identifies performance metrics that meet the requirements of both—BER for classical signals and key rate for quantum signals.

In addition, several important parameters that can impact the performance of a CV-QKD signal for a full C-band dense WDM (DWDM) system have not yet been sufficiently researched. These parameters can be essential to manage quantum-classical coexistence effectively. Such parameters can be exposed to a software-defined networking (SDN) based network architecture. This architecture enables centralized control of network resources through programmable software applications. Thus, it can improve the efficiency and dynamic management of such coexistence [18]. When a QKD connection request occurs (e.g., between transmitter (Tx)/Alice and receiver (Rx)/Bob), the SDN-enabled network architecture can make decisions under the light of these physical-layer parameters based on available resources and system requirements to optimize classical transmission and maximize the secure key rate of CV-QKD.

This work focuses on identifying such physical-layer parameters that can affect the performance of a CV-QKD system coexisting in a DWDM setting. In [17] we performed the preliminary investigation of such parameters for 8 × 200G channels. Here, we have deepened our analysis by considering a full C-band scenario with 37 dummy CCs. We have investigated the impact of the number of exchanged quantum symbols because it is relevant to the security and post-processing of CV-QKD protocol [19], impact of CCs power on CV-QKD, frequency allocation of quantum channel (QC) to improve performance of CV-QKD within the C-band, and the impact of distributed power (same power distributed over the full C-band) and concentrated power (same power concentrated on a few CCs). Moreover, for a more realistic scenario of 8 × 200G channels we have explored the performance of QC in terms of channel spacing between CC and QC to efficiently manage the available spectrum and optimal power range for QC and CCs coexistence. We have implemented CV-QKD transmission alongside classical signals using simulation software, VPIphotonics [20] to analyze these physical-layer parameters to be exposed to SDN based network architecture to make an efficient decision.

The structure of this article is as follows: Section II examines the SDN-enabled coexistence of CV-QKD and CCs within DWDM systems. This section discusses the CV-QKD protocol, security considerations, and the main impairments in a coexistence scenario. It also explores how SDN enables the coexistence of CV-QKD and CCs in DWDM systems. Here, the

flexibility of SDN is highlighted and the role of each controller is briefly described in hybrid quantum-classical environments. In Section III, the VPIphotonics coexistence test setup used to evaluate the system’s performance is outlined. Section IV presents and discusses the results, analyzing key performance metrics and the influence of different parameters on coexistence. Finally, Section V concludes the work.

II. SDN-ENABLED COEXISTENCE OF CV-QKD AND CLASSICAL CHANNELS IN DWDM SYSTEMS

To study the coexistence of CV-QKD and CCs within DWDM systems, we focus on the Gaussian-modulated coherent states (GMCS) CV-QKD protocol [7]. While Gaussian modulation remains a widely adopted approach in CV-QKD due to its well-established security proofs, discrete-modulated CV-QKD [21] has been gaining attention for its ease of implementation with existing telecom infrastructure. One major limitation is that security proofs in the finite-size regime rely on techniques that require the full discretization of Bob’s data. This approach simplifies the reverse reconciliation process by converting it into a binary symmetric channel (BSC) coding problem. However, at long distances, the BSC exhibits a high crossover probability, often exceeding 40%, making error correction significantly more challenging. The development of error-correcting codes capable of achieving high efficiency under such noise levels has not been extensively explored [22]. Despite these challenges, discrete modulation remains a promising area of research, offering potential solutions to improve the reconciliation process and enable stable, efficient long-distance key distillation.

The GMCS relies on coherent quantum states that are modulated using a bivariate Gaussian distribution, which is crucial for encoding the quantum information that is transmitted between two communicating parties, Alice and Bob. Alice prepares coherent states, reserves some for parameter estimation [7] and uses the rest for key generation. After transmission, Bob measures the received states. Using reverse reconciliation [7], Bob shares error-correction data with Alice to align their results. They then estimate channel parameters like transmittance (T) and excess noise (ζ) to ensure security against eavesdrops, aborting if risks are too high. Finally, privacy amplification removes any leaked information, producing a secure key.

We examine the key components and operational principles of GMCS protocol. A discussion of the security considerations of this protocol is included, and an analysis of excess noise and transmittance—the crucial factors impacting the performance and security of the CV-QKD system—when operated alongside CCs is conducted. Through this discussion, we aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the challenges associated with integrating CV-QKD within DWDM systems. This analysis serves as a foundation for identifying key areas that require performance optimization and ensure secure quantum communications in complex network environments. Finally, we present the high-level integration of SDN within a network where classical and CV-QKD channels coexist.

a) Components of a GMCS CV-QKD System

A GMCS CV-QKD system is made up of three main components: a Tx/Alice, a communication channel (the medium through which the quantum states are sent), and a

receiver Rx/Bob. When a large number of quantum symbols N (representing the encoded information) are transmitted, the rate at which Alice and Bob can generate a secret key fraction (r) can be estimated using Devetak-Winter formula [7] $r = \beta I_{AB} - \chi_{EB}$ which represents the amount of secure information that can be extracted from each symbol in bits/symbol. This is determined by several factors: 1) mutual information (I_{AB}) which represents the amount of information that Alice and Bob share after their communication, 2) reconciliation efficiency (β) which measures how effectively the error-correcting code used in the communication can correct any errors that might have occurred during transmission, and 3) Holevo bound (χ_{EB}) which is an upper limit on the amount of information that an eavesdropper (referred to as Eve) could potentially gain from the communication. It quantifies the relationship between what Bob observes and what Eve could have potentially captured.

b) Security Considerations

Security in this protocol is typically proven against collective attacks, a type of eavesdropping strategy [7]. In the context of Gaussian-modulated states, these attacks are considered optimal, implying that if the protocol is secure against them, it is generally secure [23]. As the number of transmitted symbols N increases, the key rate calculation starts approaching the asymptotic limit. However, in real-world applications, the number of symbols exchanged between Alice and Bob is finite. Moreover, a composable security analysis (i.e. the composition of secure subsystems must be secure) must be performed since the protocol is composed of different stages affecting the resulting secret key. These practical concerns can be addressed using a more complex approach, called finite-size formalism, [24] which considers the limitations of a finite N and ensures that the overall security of the protocol is maintained. Furthermore, security analyses of CV-QKD protocols continue to evolve, with recent works demonstrating robust security proofs even in practical, finite-size implementations [25]. We consider both asymptotic and finite size formalisms in this work. The finite-size secret key rate is given by $r' = \frac{n}{N}(\beta I'_{AB} - \chi'_{EB} - \Delta(n))$ Where N is the total number of symbols, n is the numbers of symbol used for parameter estimation (typically $N/2$), β is the reconciliation efficiency, I'_{AB} is the mutual information in the finite size regime, χ'_{EB} is the Holevo bound in the finite size regime, and $\Delta(n)$ relates to the security of privacy amplification.

c) Analysis of Transmittance and Excess Noise in Quantum-Classical Coexistence Scenario

In a coexistence scenario, the GMCS protocol is multiplexed with CCs in DWDM. The key characteristic parameters are transmittance (T) and excess noise (ζ). The transmittance $T = T_{ch} \eta_{det}$ comprises the channel transmittance (T_{ch}) that accounts for attenuation of the signal due to propagation, and the detection losses at the detector of Bob, which are characterized by the detection efficiency (η_{det}).

Excess noise (ζ) can be broken down into three components: ζ_o , ζ_{NLI} , and ζ_{SpRS} . The first component ζ_o represents the intrinsic noise of the stand-alone CV-QKD system that includes imperfect modulation, quantization of analog-to-digital converter, detector's noise, intensity noise, phase noise, etc. In

this work value is assumed to be fixed to 0.01 shot noise unit (SNU), justified by testing the same configuration experimentally in [16]. The second component ζ_{NLI} accounts for noise arising from fiber nonlinearities, such as self-phase modulation, cross-phase modulation, and four-wave mixing. This type of noise is particularly significant in DWDM systems operating in the C-band, where high-power CCs are located close to the QC, potentially causing signal distortions that degrade the quality of the quantum communication. We analyze ζ_{NLI} using VPIphotonics. The third component, ζ_{SpRS} , is caused by spontaneous Raman scattering (SpRS), which is a major source of interference when there is significant spacing between the CCs and the QC. This type of noise occurs due to interactions between photons and phonons, which can cause photons to shift to different wavelengths, potentially interfering with other channels. Depending on whether a phonon is excited or de-excited, photons at higher (Stokes) or lower (anti-Stokes) wavelengths than the original may be produced. The excess noise component ζ_{SpRS} can be modeled according to [29] as

$$\zeta_{SpRS} = \sum_i \left(\frac{\lambda^3}{hc^2} \right) \rho_i(f) P_{fwd}^i L e^{-\alpha L}. \quad (1)$$

where, P_{fwd}^i is the input power of the i^{th} CC sent in the forward direction, f is the frequency of the QC, h is Planck's constant, c is the speed of light, and $\rho_i(f)$ is the Raman scattering coefficient of i^{th} CC as a function of f . ζ_{SpRS} can also be analyzed through VPIphotonics which we have used for its simulation. The analytical equation is used to explain complex scenarios in Section IV.

d) SDN-Enabled Coexistence

The basic relevant aspects of the SDN-enabled coexistence architecture are shown in Fig. 1. The primary focus of this work is to identify the physical-layer parameters that are the most relevant for exposure to SDN, rather than delving into the specifics of the SDN architecture itself. The details of the SDN architecture can be found in [18].

At the core of this architecture is the SDN Orchestrator, which serves as the central management entity. The SDN

Fig. 1 SDN-enabled network architecture supporting classical-quantum coexistence

Fig. 2 Test Setup of CV-QKD coexistence with classical channels

orchestrator is responsible for overseeing the overall network operations, ensuring seamless interaction between the various controllers that manage different aspects of the network. It communicates with the software defined (SD)-optical network controller and with the SD-QKD network controller.

For the sake of explanation, we show two SD-QKD nodes (node 1 and node 2) controlled by SD-QKD Network Controller. This controller ensures the correct operation of the SD-QKD nodes by interacting with SD-QKD node controllers within their respective nodes. It is dedicated to managing the CV-QKD aspect of the network such as configuring their wavelength. Each SD-QKD Node contains a QKD Module designated for generating and transmitting quantum states, making them integral to the network's security infrastructure. The SD-optical network controller manages the traditional optical network infrastructure which means it handles the routing and transmission of CCs and their power levels, ensuring they are effectively integrated within the network having CV-QKD signals in it. This architecture envisions the use of reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexers (ROADMs) to dynamically establish and manage both QCs and CCs.

Key programmable parameters and relevant interfaces include ETSI GS QKD 004 and 014 for the key management system, and ETSI GS QKD 015 for configuring and monitoring the SD-QKD Node [4][18]. SD-QKD network controller development is in progress which extends the open-source, cloud-native ETSI TeraFlow SDN (TFS) controller [26][27]. The SDN-enabled QKD process provides clients with key pairs for secure communication. It starts when a client requests the SD-QKD network controller to create a secure communication channel with another client. This request prompts the SDN orchestrator to allocate resources and configure the network. The SD-QKD network controller checks if QKD resources are available and works with the SD-optical network controller to set up a lightpath for the QC and CC [28]. This involves allocating, for example, optical spectrum and adjusting power levels. After that, the QKD nodes establish a secure link, and the generated states are transferred securely between the QKD nodes.

For simplicity, we refer to this hierarchical SDN approach as the *SDN control system* throughout this work.

The parameters to be explored in this work can be shared with the *SDN control system* that takes the decision of efficiently managing the coexistence of CCs and QC. Since T depends on the system losses, the fiber characteristics and the type of detectors used, the *SDN control system* cannot use these factors in optimization. ξ_0 noise is intrinsic to the CV-QKD

manufacturing equipment and is considered fixed, as it does not contribute to SDN optimization processes. Since ξ_{NLI} noise is influenced by the power levels of CCs, it can be managed by the *SDN control system*. Finally, ξ_{SPRS} noise is affected by the power levels of CCs and the wavelength used for QC, thus, its characteristics can also be exposed to the *SDN control system*.

III. TEST SETUP OF COEXISTENCE SCENARIO

The diagram in Fig. 2 illustrates the CV-QKD coexistence setup, as used in this study and implemented in VPIphotonics software. In the depicted test setup, two SD-QKD nodes are considered: one at the Tx and one at the Rx. At the Tx, the QKD module Tx (inset 1) generates QCs using GMCSs protocol. This is achieved with a laser source operating at a frequency of 193.2 THz (unless stated otherwise) and a linewidth of 10 kHz. The generated laser carrier is then modulated by an amplitude modulator (AM) and a phase modulator (PM), allowing the encoding of quantum information onto the optical signal. A variable optical attenuator (VOA) is placed at the output of the QKD module to fine-tune the modulation variance (V_{mod}), which is critical for maintaining the security of the quantum key distribution process [7]. The symbol rate of quantum symbols is assumed to be 31.25 MHz.

Two scenarios are examined: (a) the system simulates a full C-band optical spectrum with different dummy CCs (without modulation format effects). These range from 192.1 THz (ITU-T channel (Ch) 21) to 196 THz (Ch 60); for a quantum-classical channel spacing of 200 GHz and (b) eight dual-polarized (DP) classical signals with 200 Gb/s data rates, a symbol rate of 32 Gbaud, and 16-QAM modulation format for a quantum-classical channel spacing of 100 GHz. Both configurations are evaluated in the following section.

The CCs are multiplexed with QC using a DWDM MUX with 100-GHz channel spacing. This combined signal is transmitted over a standard single-mode fiber (SSMF). The optical spectrum after multiplexing in case (i), is shown in the diagram (inset 2) with a power level of -15.56 dBm per CC. Upon transmission through the fiber, the QC is extracted from the multiplexed signal using an optical rectangular bandpass filter (BPF) with a 50 GHz bandwidth and 40 dB stop-band attenuation. This filtering is essential to isolate the quantum signal from the surrounding classical signals. At the receiver side, the QKD module Rx (inset 3) performs phase-diversity detection, which involves using a 90-degree optical hybrid and two pairs of balanced photodetectors. This configuration allows for accurate measurement of the quantum states, facilitating the key extraction process.

For the purpose of these simulations, the local oscillator (LO) required for coherent detection is derived from the same laser used in the QKD module at the transmitter. For link distances exceeding the laser coherence length, the setup effectively functions as if two independent lasers are used. From a security perspective, a local LO must be used [7]. However, in this work, a beam splitter (BS) is employed for ease of implementation, as the primary focus is on evaluating the impact of CCs on the QC rather than the security vulnerabilities associated with transmitting the LO from Tx to Rx. In practical implementations, using a local LO would not alter the findings of this study. A BS directs a portion of the laser signal towards the Rx, ensuring synchronization and phase reference for the detection process. Additionally, a parameter estimation process is incorporated, which includes error reconciliation with a reconciliation efficiency of $\beta = 0.95$ for asymptotic approximation and parameters of [24] for finite size formalism.

IV. RESULTS AND INSIGHTS INTO THE KEY FACTORS INFLUENCING THE PERFORMANCE OF CV-QKD AND CLASSICAL CHANNELS

To determine the key factors impacting the performance of CV-QKD systems in the presence of CCs, we first explore how the number of exchanged symbols affects QKD distance for a given security. Then, for the case of dummy unmodulated CCs we evaluate the impact of different power levels of CCs and examine the effect of QC frequency allocation in the C-band. We also compare the performance of concentrated vs. distributed power across CCs. Additionally, for $8 \times 200\text{G}$ 16-QAM modulated CCs we investigate the influence of classical-quantum channel spacing adjustments. Finally, we assess CC recovery to determine optimal power levels for transmission.

The performance evaluation focuses on two key metrics: ζ and r (or r'). We assume $\eta_{det}=0.5$, insertion losses to add and drop the QC is taken as 1.2 dB each [16], and we take $V_{mod}=4.4$ SNU throughout the discussion unless stated otherwise.

Impact of Number of Exchanged Symbols on Secret Key Fraction

The graph in Fig. 3 shows the relationship between the number of exchanged symbols N (x-axis, on a logarithmic scale) and the finite size r' in bits per symbol (y-axis) for a 10-km link. The red line represents a threshold below which the value of r' becomes negative, indicating that secure key generation is not feasible in this region. The orange line represents the asymptotic limit. As shown in the graph, the value of r' grows as the number of exchanged symbols increases, eventually approaching the asymptotic limit of up to 98.51% at around 1×10^{13} symbols. Notably, below approximately 1×10^{10} symbols, the finite size r' remains negative, confirming that secure key generation is impossible below this point. This demonstrates that a sufficiently high number of exchanged symbols are essential to achieve a positive and reliable secret key rate for secure communication. Also, if the number of the exchanged symbols are reduced to 1×10^{10} a positive r' is still achievable but with a penalty of 20.84% (79.16% of asymptotic) of reduction in the value of r' .

As the number of exchanged quantum symbols increases, the secret key rate improves and approaches the asymptotic

limit. If the error correction is done with fixed number of symbols, the fact on getting closer to the asymptotic limit adds latency on the key generation. In many practical scenarios where latency is not the primary concern, this trade-off is manageable. This enables the SDN control system to optimize the number of exchanged symbols based on the targeted value of security level, distance, and r .

Fig. 3 r' as a function of number of exchanged symbols

The following analyses examine two scenarios described in Section III. Scenario (a) considers unmodulated dummy channels, while Scenario (b) investigates $8 \times 200\text{G}$ modulated channels. For Scenario (a), a quantum-classical channel spacing of 200 GHz is assumed unless specified otherwise. Scenario (b) evaluates the potential to reduce this spacing further to align with the 100 GHz ITU fixed grid. Both scenarios are evaluated in the asymptotic regime. For the finite-size case, the same conclusions apply, provided that a sufficiently large N is used to either approach the asymptotic limit or balance the trade-off of latency, as discussed in the analysis of Fig. 3

Scenario (a): Dummy Unmodulated Classical Channels

1. Quantum Channel Performance Evaluation with 37 Classical Channels

The graph in Fig. 4 evaluates the performance of a CV-QKD system in the presence of 37 dummy CCs under different launch power levels. QC is situated at Ch 32 whereas the CCs are situated from Ch 21 to Ch 30 and from Ch 34 to Ch 60. It highlights a clear trade-off between r and CCs power. At lower launch powers the system maintains a relatively high r and ζ remains low, allowing the generation of keys. However, as launch power increases, the r drops and ζ grows with secure transmission becoming impossible beyond total launch power of 11 dBm (r becomes negative). This enables the *SDN control system* to play with the power of CCs based on the required value of r . It also helps to determine the maximum power that can be launched into the fiber alongside the CV-QKD signal while still achieving a positive r . SDN control system dynamically monitors network conditions, such as r and CC power fluctuations. Based on real-time feedback, the SDN control system can adjust CC power levels to maintain an optimal balance between quantum and classical channel performance. For example, if the power of CCs exceeds a threshold where QKD performance is compromised, SDN can issue commands to reduce CC power. This adaptive control ensures that both quantum and classical signals maintain reliable transmission while minimizing impairments.

Fig. 4 Impact of classical channel power on CV-QKD

2. Effect of Quantum Channel Frequency Allocation

For this analysis we start by examining the case of a single CC and QC, describing the impact of SpRS. In this case the insertion losses are considered as zero and η_{det} as 1. The graph in Fig. 5 analyzes the impact of SpRS from a CC at Ch 32 on a QC placed at spectral locations varying from Ch 21 to Ch 60, within a DWDM system. For example., when the QC was placed at Ch 41, the ξ_{SpRS} was found to be 1.98 mSNU. The inset provides a detailed view of the optical spectrum at 0 dBm, at different frequencies as the QC shifts across the spectrum. The ξ_{SpRS} was found to be higher in the Stokes region compared to the anti-Stokes region. This indicates that, although, for one CC and one QC, positioning the QC closer to the CC reduces ξ_{SpRS} and if a channel closer to CC is not available then placing it at anti-stokes region is better than at stokes region.

Fig. 5 Spontaneous Raman scattering noise

However, the scenario becomes more complex with multiple CCs, as each CC creates its own SpRS profile and other non-linear effects come into play as well, that can affect the QC differently.

To evaluate the impact of SpRS of multiple CCs on the QC, we analyze the QC's performance at different positions (Ch 22, Ch 32, and Ch 59) in presence of 37 dummy CCs. Two adjacent channels are left empty to make SpRS dominant. This analysis is illustrated in Fig. 6. The results show that as CC power increases, the QC performance (r value) decreases. At low launch power levels below 6.6 dBm, each QC position gives similar performance. However, at power levels exceeding 7.6 dBm, performance differences become evident: Ch 59 outperforms Ch 32, while Ch 32 performs better than Ch 22.

This indicates that placing the QC at higher frequency channels with respect to the CCs—such as positioning it at Ch 59 improves system's performance by enhancing the r value. Another interesting point is that not only does the value of r improve but also the total supported launch power improves when QC is at Ch 32 and Ch 59. The max supported power is reduced to 9.8 dBm for the case of Ch 22 which was 11 dBm for Ch 32 (Fig. 4). These findings provide valuable insights for *SDN control system*, suggesting that strategic QC placement can optimize performance based on the required value of r .

Fig. 6 Channel placement effects on CV-QKD

3. Analytical Analysis and Verification for Quantum Channel Placement

To address the question of why the QC performs better at higher frequencies than at lower ones, we investigated the effects of SpRS analytically. We used the Raman scattering profile, $\rho(f)$, from [30] at 1550 nm and approximated different $\rho(f)$ profiles at various frequencies by shifting the frequencies while keeping the profile constant. This is illustrated in Fig. 7, which shows the QC positioned at Ch 22, marked by red dashed lines. The figure demonstrates that QC crosses different points on multiple $\rho(f)$ profiles, indicating that the cumulative impact of SpRS on the QC is the sum of these profiles, as described in Eq. (1). An interesting observation is that the QC at higher frequency channel as Ch 59 would exhibit crossover points of relatively smaller magnitude compared to the QCs at Ch 22 resulting in better performance at higher frequencies

Fig. 7 Raman scattering coefficient for multiple classical channels when quantum channel is placed at Ch 22

Fig. 8 shows the summation of Raman scattering coefficient profiles for channels Ch 22, Ch 32, and Ch 59, with the vertical axis representing the total coefficient $\sum \rho_i(f)$ scaled by 10^7 .

Among the three, Ch 22 has the highest summation value, indicating it crosses the most significant magnitude points, followed by Ch 32, which exhibits a slightly lower value. Ch 59 shows the lowest summation, reflecting fewer or less intense crossover points compared to the other channels. This trend demonstrates a clear reduction in Raman scattering intensity, from Ch 22 to Ch 59.

Fig. 8 Summation of crossover points of Raman scattering coefficient profiles

Under this assumption, Fig. 9 shows the forward SpRS effects for different fiber lengths for QC at Ch 22, Ch 32, and Ch 59 obtained from VPIphotonics. The results clearly show that Ch 59 experiences less SpRS interference than Ch 32, and Ch 32 performs better than Ch 22. This confirms our analytical approach, proving that positioning the QC at higher frequencies results in better system performance.

Fig. 9 SpRS as a function of fiber length at different QC frequencies

4. Power Distribution Across Channels

We investigate the effects of distributed versus concentrated power in CCs on the performance of CV-QKD under conditions where ζ_{SpRS} is the dominant noise source. This analysis is conducted with a 200 GHz channel spacing between QC and CCs whereas the QC is fixed at Ch 32. Two cases are examined: (i) where CCs are distributed on both sides of the QC and (ii) where CC power is concentrated in either higher or lower frequency channels of C-band relative to the QC.

In case (i), CCs are added on both sides of the QC as shown in Fig. 10a. For 2 CCs, they are placed at Ch 30 and Ch 34. When 8 CCs are used, additional channels are introduced at 100 GHz intervals, spanning Ch 27 to Ch 30 and Ch 34 to Ch 37. For 16 CCs, four more channels are added on each side of the QC. In the case of 37 CCs, the channels are distributed across Ch 21 to Ch 30 and Ch 34 to Ch 60.

In case (ii), CC power is concentrated on one side of the QC. For 8 CCs, they are either concentrated at lower frequencies (8 CCs-L) from Ch 22 to Ch 29 or at higher frequencies (8 CCs-H) from Ch 52 to Ch 59 as shown in Fig. 10b.

The results reveal interesting trends. In case (i), the performance of 2 CCs and 8 CCs is similar, while 16 CCs perform comparably at lower power levels (below 8 dBm) but degrade significantly at higher powers. The 37 CCs scenario performs the worst across all power levels, indicating that concentrating power in fewer channels mitigates the detrimental impact of SpRS on the QC.

In case (ii), concentrating power in 8 CCs-L provides better performance than the 37 CCs setup. However, concentrating power in 8 CCs-H results in a significant performance drop, even below that of the 37 CCs case.

This suggests that the performance as a function of power distribution across channels depends upon the number of CCs, the power of CCs and their spectral placement relative to the QC. These findings play an important role for an *SDN control system* to manage and assign resources.

Fig. 10 (a) Spectrum when CCs are added on both sides of the QC, (b) Spectrum when CC power is concentrated on one side of the QC, and (c) Impact of distributed vs concentrated power

Scenario (b): 8 × 200G Modulated Channels

1. Performance with Modulated Channels

The graph in Fig. 11 shows the performance of CV-QKD alongside 8 × 200G CCs and the effect of channel spacing between QC and CCs (blue and orange continuous curves). We evaluate the value of r as a function of total launch power (dBm) in a system with eight modulated CCs surrounding a central QC at Ch 32. The blue curve represents a 100 GHz spacing between the quantum and CCs, with CCs placed on Ch 28 to Ch 31 and Ch 33 to Ch 36. At higher power levels, the value of r drops

significantly, indicating rapid performance degradation due to nonlinear impairments [15]. At 10 dBm, key generation is not achievable. To explore potential improvements at this power level, we analyzed the orange curve, which represents a wider 200 GHz channel spacing (CCs positioned from Ch 27 to Ch 30 and Ch 34 to Ch 37). With this increased spacing, a positive value of r is achieved, and the configuration sustains higher r values across different power levels. At 9 dBm, the performance shows an improvement of approximately 2.62-fold. This result demonstrates that sufficient channel spacing between QC and CCs is crucial to minimize interference and maintain a higher r , especially at higher launch powers.

Additionally, we compare the performance of modulated and unmodulated (dummy) channels, shown by the dashed blue and orange curves. The orange dashed curve represents a system with 200 GHz spacing, and its behavior closely follows the orange continuous curve, which corresponds to modulated signals. This suggests that at wider spacing, the difference between modulated and unmodulated signals is minimal. However, the blue dashed curve does not follow the blue continuous curve, which represents modulated signals with 100 GHz spacing. This indicates that when the CCs are closer to the QC, the modulation format significantly influences nonlinear effects, making them more noticeable. This is expected, as modulated signals introduce intensity fluctuations and broad spectral occupation. In contrast, with sufficient channel spacing (200 GHz), the impact of modulation format is not prominent, and performance is closer to that of an unmodulated (dummy) channel.

Fig. 11 Impact of channel power on r with channel spacing between QC and CC is 100 GHz (blue) and 200 GHz (orange)

2. Joint Performance Evaluation of Classical and Quantum Channels in DWDM Systems

In this analysis, we consider $8 \times 200\text{G}$ CCs alongside a QC positioned at Ch 32. Four CCs are placed on each side of the QC, spaced 100 GHz apart, with a channel spacing of 100 GHz at each side of QC from Ch 28 to Ch 31 and from Ch 33 to Ch 36. Table 1 assesses error-free recovery of CC Ch 28 (192.8 THz) with a forward error correction [31] threshold of 1×10^{-2} [32] under various optical signal to noise ratio (OSNR) conditions (30 dB, 25 dB, and 20dB) and power levels. All classical signals regardless of the receiver's sensitivity are assumed to be detectable. Only the power levels where CV-QKD has positive key generation are analyzed. At 10 dBm total power that corresponds to 0.969 dBm per channel the value of

r becomes negative (Fig. 11). At OSNR of 30 dB, CC maintains reliable transmission across a wide power range of $[-26, 0]$ dBm per channel which corresponds to $[-16.96, 9.03]$ dBm total power, though they fail below -26 dBm (which may increase in the real-world networks depending on the receiver's sensitivity). At 25 dB OSNR this range reduces to $[-24, 0]$ dBm which corresponds to $[-14.96, 9.03]$ dBm total power. At 20 dB OSNR, error-free recovery of CC becomes impossible across all power levels. This highlights the importance of optimizing power levels for CCs. Moreover, key generation for CV-QKD remains possible at all power levels below 1 dBm per channel, meaning CC power does not need to be excessively low. This ensures that CCs can still be transmitted at suitable power levels to make sure their error-free recovery.

These insights offer valuable guidance for an *SDN control system* to balance power allocation among CCs, ensuring reliable transmission of both classical and quantum channels based on OSNR conditions.

Table 1 Performance of CCs and QC at 10 km with 100 GHz CC-QC spacing

Power per channel (dBm)	Error free Recovery Ch 28			CV-QKD Key Rate
	OSNR 30 dB	OSNR 25 dB	OSNR 20 dB	
-30 to -27	No	No	No	Positive
-26 to -25	Yes	No	No	Positive
-24 to 0	Yes	Yes	No	Positive
1	Yes	Yes	No	Negative

In the end we would like to highlight the main sources of noise and the summary of the key insights of Section IV. In all simulations involving optical fiber with VPIphotonics, both ξ_{SpRS} and ξ_{NLI} are considered. However, the dominance of each noise source varies depending on the scenario.

For example, in Fig. 5, where only one QC and one CC are present, the NLI effects are minimal, and the curve closely follows the SpRS noise profile from [30], indicating that SpRS is the dominant noise source. Similarly, in Fig. 6, we analyze the effect of QC placement with 200 GHz spacing from the CCs. The results align with the expectation that SpRS dominates at this channel spacing, which is further validated analytically in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. These figures confirm that, with 200 GHz QC-CC spacing, SpRS remains the primary limiting factor.

However, in Fig. 11, where the QC-CC spacing is reduced to 100 GHz, a steep degradation in the secret key fraction r suggests the contribution of additional noise sources. At higher power levels, NLI effects become more pronounced. When the spacing is increased back to 200 GHz, the impact of NLI is noticeably reduced, providing further evidence that increasing the QC-CC spacing helps mitigate nonlinear impairments.

The summary of the key points of the results can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2 Summary of the key insights of the results

Parameter	Impact
Number of exchanged symbols	Security depends on N .
	Secret key fraction decreases when N decreases.
Power of CC	QC becomes very detrimental at high power levels
QC position	For a single CC, placing it closer to the CC is better.

	For full C-band occupancy, positioning QC at higher frequencies relative to CCs is preferable.
Channel Spacing	Placing CCs too close to QC can significantly deteriorate QC performance. This can be improved by increasing the channel spacing between CCs and QC.
Power distribution across CC	It depends upon the number of CCs, the power of CCs and their spectral placement relative to the QC and should be carefully analyzed.
BER and key fraction	The optimal power range for supporting both CCs (BER) and QC (secret key fraction) varies significantly with OSNR and must be calculated appropriately.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we examined the key physical-layer parameters influencing the coexistence of CV-QKD and CCs within a DWDM system operating in the C-band. We analyzed, number of transmitted quantum symbols, CC power levels, QC allocation within the C-band, power distribution among CCs, channel spacing between CCs, and the power ranges compatible with both CCs and QC.

We found that for short distances and low key-rates, the number of quantum symbols exchanged does not need to reach the asymptotic limit. However, achieving the secret key fraction closer to 98.51% of the asymptotic regime on a 10-km link requires transmitting approximately 1×10^{13} quantum symbols.

CC power significantly affects CV-QKD performance. For example, in a DWDM setup with 37 CCs on a 100 GHz grid, a total launch power of up to 11 dBm can be supported over a 10-km link when the QC is positioned at 193.2 THz with 200 GHz channel spacing from CCs.

Additionally, placing the QC at higher frequencies relative to CCs improves both the secret key fraction and the maximum CC power supported. For instance, positioning the QC at 195.9 THz yields better performance than placing it at 193.2 THz or 192.2 THz. Notably, placing the QC at 192.2 THz reduces the maximum supported CC power to 9.8 dBm.

The relationship between power distribution across CCs is complex and depends on factors such as the number of active CCs, their power levels, and their proximity to the QC.

In a configuration with 8×200 GHz modulated CCs, placing CCs 100 GHz from the QC introduces nonlinear noise but still supports a positive secret key fraction. Increasing the spacing to 200 GHz further enhances CV-QKD performance.

Joint performance analysis demonstrated that, with a 100 GHz spacing and a 30 dB OSNR for CCs, a CC launch power range of -16.96 to 9.03 dBm allows for both error-free CC recovery and positive key rate generation over a 10-km link.

Overall, our findings underline the intricate interplay between CV-QKD and CCs and offer practical strategies for optimizing their coexistence in DWDM systems using SDN control system.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been partially funded by the "Ministerio de Asuntos Económicos y Transformación Digital" and the European Union-NextGenerationEU in the frameworks of the "Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia" and of the "Mecanismo de Recuperación y Resiliencia" under reference 6G-OPENSEC-KEYS (TSI-063000-2021-61), by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033/FEDER, UE through the RELAMPAGO (PID2021-127916OBI00) project, by European

Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101092766 (ALLEGRO Project) and by EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation program EC Digital QUARTER (101091588).

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